

COMBINATION OF LINGUADIDACTICS AND INTERACTIVE METHODS

Yuldashova Nargiza Abdukholiq qizi,
*Teacher, English Department,
‘Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural
Mechanization Engineers’ National Research
University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan*

Annotation. *The purpose of the article is to show developing the lingo-didactic foundations of language teaching and ways to solve problems that arise in practice. The tasks are to reveal the relevance of the use of interactive methods, to analyze the specific features of language teaching, to demonstrate the effectiveness of the combined use of language didactics and interactive methods.*

Key terms: *didactic basis, linguodidactics, monolingualism, bilingualism, interactive method, situational-game, simulation, situation analysis.*

The pedagogical and philological cycle of sciences currently being developed in Uzbekistan is faced with the tasks of intensifying the search for the foundations of new didactics, vocabulary, text theory, translation studies, etc. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov posed such an extremely important problem at the ninth session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan (August 29, 1997): “We need to quickly prepare a methodology for accelerating the study of foreign languages, based on national features [2].

The science of linguodidactics develops the general of the theory of language teaching, that is, it deals with the methodological basis of language teaching / learning. These include issues such as the goals, content, methods (principles), tools, methods of scientific research, and the relationship of language teaching with other disciplines: teaching language aspects (vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation material) and types of speech activities (listening, speaking, reading, writing), as well as the organization of the learning process, etc [3].

Unlike math or other subjects, language classrooms use audio materials and visual aids as media. In this case, language plays two main roles at the same time: the subject of the lesson and the means of explaining the subject. In other words, the teacher of the Higher Education Institution must first use the language as a source of instruction or material. As a result, the student learns English with the help of English. Of course, it is difficult to achieve such a success. Given that the first thing required of a teacher is field knowledge, his or her ability to use vocabulary in the classroom will help the student to master the lesson more easily.

It is appropriate to look at lingo-didactics not as a set of professional vocabulary that serve to make the lesson boring and complicated, unnecessary and insignificant for the teacher and the student, but as a tool to increase lesson

effectiveness and engage students in a deeper understanding of the methodological foundations of science. Indeed, Abdullah Avloni (1878 - 1934) put the problem of science at the forefront of all his research. "Fortunately," he wrote, "all our lives, our health, our happiness, our wealth, our life, our generosity, our zeal, our world and the hereafter are connected with science." Therefore, we must do our best to get rid of ignorance, which is the enemy of our body, without wasting time reading and knowing. [1].

Linguo-didactics is a practical linguistic science that takes into account both the teaching of a foreign language and the acquisition of a foreign language. Linguodidactics studies the general laws of language teaching, develops methods and tools for teaching a particular language depending on the didactic objectives, the influence of monolingualism (monolingualism) or bilingualism (bilingualism) on language learning and solves a number of related problems.

So, let's talk about some of the comments on the science of foreign language teaching (linguodidactics). Linguodidactics is derived from the Latin “lingua” “language” and the Greek “didacticos” “teaching” and is a science that deals with the creation of a general theory of language teaching. The term was first coined by the Russian linguist N.M. Shansky introduces that this science is designed to deal with the study of the problems of language teaching. The main tasks of linguodidactics are to identify similarities and differences between languages, to analyze the content and structure of the studied language, to solve such problems as to establish the linguistic minimums necessary for the teaching process.

Interactive learning is organized in such a way that almost all students are involved in the learning process. Student collaboration means that everyone contributes, sharing knowledge, ideas, and types of activities. As a type of interactive technology, multimedia is the full spectrum of information technology using a variety of software and tools that perform data processing in audio and visual mode to enhance the most effective impact on the user. Multimedia transmits audio, data and images over local, regional and global networks. Special programs for real-time communication allow the teacher to organize the team work of remote users with a program running on a local computer. Interactive work mode creates an integrated information environment of pictures, animation, photo, video, sound, text, where any student of any age can find completely new opportunities for lifelong learning.

When teaching a foreign language, the teacher must first take into account the level of knowledge of the student. Because every student develops a certain

knowledge and skills in a foreign language in high school, and teaching a foreign language in high school is relatively complex and in-depth.

When a teacher teaches a foreign language, the student must have the ability to arouse interest in the language. When teaching a foreign language, not only the language itself (phonetics, grammar, vocabulary, structure) but also the history, customs, culture, great scholars and other important aspects of the country associated with that language. should also be taught.

Interactive learning technologies include clearly planned learning outcomes, interactive methods, tools and forms that stimulate the learning process, cognitive and mental conditions, and procedures for achieving planned outcomes [10]. Thus, interactive technologies encompass the interactive methods that a teacher uses in their work.

Teaching language is at the center of world linguistics today, along with a variety of other topics. One of the most difficult tasks today is to find "linguadistics with methods" that has a broader meaning in modern linguistics and is being studied in greater depth. Linguadidacts is one of the most important areas of modern linguistic research[14]. Nowadays, the growth of the problem of linguadidacts is considered, on the one hand, due to the dynamic development of teaching process and the proliferation of new concepts, on the other hand, due to insufficient study of issues such as the process of formation, development and function of terms. Each department or education system develops specific linguadidacts according to its nature and methods. Such specialized linguadidacts is an important part of scientific research.

In conclusion, Interactive methods are based on the dialogue between the student and the teacher in the teaching of foreign languages, vocabulary and terms, so the learning process involves all students in cognitive activity. It means the exchange of ideas, knowledge and experience which is based on linguadidactics. By participating in interactive activities, students learn to collaborate, think logically, analyze information, and solve problems. Prerequisites for effective language learning are free communication, expression of opinions and mutual respect. The use of interactive technologies is not the goal, but it should be seen as a means of creating the necessary conditions for communicatively effective teaching.

In short, the regulation of linguadidacts is an important issue not only in the scientific field, but also in Teaching process. The effectiveness of the regulation of linguadidacts is evident in the following cases where the vocabulary is directly used: in the correct organization of vocational education, in oral communication in

industrial practice, in correspondence in scientific and production processes, in typography, in translating foreign literature.

References:

1. Abdulla Avloniy. Turkiy guliston yoxud axloq. „O‘qituvchi“, 1992
2. I.Karimov «Barkamol avlod orzusi». T.: O‘zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2000. P86
3. J. Jalolov, Chet til o‘qitish metodikasi „O‘qituvchi“ Toshkent-2013.
4. Jalolov J.Jahon lingvodidaktikasining zamonaviy konseptual yangilanish bosqich xususida//Horijiy filologiya. №1 (30). – Samarqand, 2009. pp91-95.
5. Джусупов М. Лингводидактика и методика в полинаучной системе языкового образования. //Русский язык за рубежом, 2009, № 2, pp26-32
6. КимВ.Н., КимТ.С. Социально-политическая терминология–Т., . 2009. С.
7. Lingvodidaktika kak teoritecheskaya osnova obucheniya yazika. Elektronniy resurs: <http://works.doklad.ru/view/NRkF6riOIeo.html>. Data obrasheniya: 03.04.2019.
8. L.Konoplyanik, Interactive methods of teaching foreign languages in higher Education in: Materials of II International Scientific Conference "Modern trends in teaching a second language at schools and institutions of higher education ", Gorlovka, HDPIIM, 2011. - p.p. 84-85.
9. H.Stern, Fundamental Concepts of Language Teaching, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1983.
10. O.I. Pometun, Current lesson. Interactive learning technologies, scientific method, Kyiv, Publishing A.S.K., 2004.
11. R.Blair, Innovation approaches to language teaching, New York, Newbury House, 2010.